

FORMULATION OF SOLUTIONS OF SOME CLASSES OF STANDARD BI-QUADRATIC CONGRUENCE OF COMPOSITE MODULUS**Prof. B M Roy**

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, some classes of solvable standard bi-quadratic congruence of composite modulus are formulated. The formulae established are tested true using some suitable examples. Formulation makes it easy to find all the solutions quickly. It is time-saving and simple. A very little literature about solvable standard bi-quadratic congruence of composite modulus is found in the literature of mathematics. Formulation is the merit of the paper.

KEYWORDS:

Bi-quadratic residues, Binomial Theorem, Bi-quadratic congruence, Composite modulus.

INTRODUCTION

A congruence of the type $x^4 \equiv a \pmod{m}$ is called a bi-quadratic congruence. If m is a composite integer, then it is called a bi-quadratic congruence of composite modulus. If m is a prime, then it is called a bi-quadratic congruence of prime modulus. The value of x that satisfies the congruence is called its solution. If a is bi-quadratic residue of m , the congruence: $x^4 \equiv a \pmod{m}$ is called solvable. If b is a residue of m , and $b^4 \equiv a \pmod{m}$, then a is called bi-quadratic residue of m .

The author already formulated some classes of standard cubic congruence of composite modulus and the papers are published in different international journals. Those papers are liked by the readers and the author got an up-thrust from it and planned to write papers on the formulation of standard bi-quadratic congruence of composite modulus.

LITERATURE-REVIEW

Referring many books of Number Theory and surfing on Internet, no formulation is found in the literature. Only a definition and two problems of finding bi-quadratic residues are seen [1]. Thus, a very little literature about bi-quadratic congruence is present. There is no formulation and no suitable method found in the literature except the Chinese Remainder Theorem in which one has to solve the separated congruence and using the said theorem, complete solutions are obtained [2], which has its own demerits. Readers found it very difficult to find solutions of the bi-quadratic congruence. In the book of Zuckerman et al, only a bi-quadratic congruence in the exercise is mentioned which is not solvable [3].

OBJECTIVES: NEED OF RESEARCH

The standard bi-quadratic congruence is neglected by the earlier mathematicians and do no research on it. It is a very important topic in Number Theory. No one showed interest to do some research on the topic. To have an easy method of finding solutions, the author tried his best to formulate the congruence and presented his efforts in this paper, because the author knows the only way out is the formulation. It is a time-saving attempt of the author.

PROBLEM-STATEMENT

The problem is “To formulate some classes of standard solvable bi-quadratic congruence of composite modulus of the type:

- (1) $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n}$
- (2) $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n \cdot b}$; $b \neq 4l$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Consider the said congruence: $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n}$.

Then, for $x = 4^{n-1}k \pm a$, $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$x^4 = (4^{n-1}k \pm a)^4$$

Expanding using binomial theorem, one get

$$\begin{aligned} x^4 &= (4^{n-1}k)^4 \pm 4 \cdot (4^{n-1}k)^3 \cdot a + \frac{4 \cdot 3}{1 \cdot 2} (4^{n-1}k)^2 a^2 \pm \frac{4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} (4^{n-1})^1 a^3 + a^4 \\ &= a^4 + 4^n (\dots) \\ &\equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $x = 4^{n-1}k \pm a$ satisfies the congruence and hence is a solution of it.

For $k = 4$, $x = 4^{n-1} \cdot 4 \pm a = 4^n \pm a \equiv \pm a \pmod{4^n}$ which is same as $k = 0$.

Similarly, for $k = 5, 6, 7$, it can be seen that the solutions are the same as for $k = 1, 2, 3$.

Therefore, all the solutions are obtained for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

Hence, the congruence has exactly eight solutions.

Consider the congruence: $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$; $b \neq 4l$; l being a positive integer.

Then, for $x = b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a$, $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$x^4 = (b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a)^4$$

Expanding using binomial theorem, one get

$$\begin{aligned} x^4 &= (b \cdot 4^{n-1}k)^4 \pm 4 \cdot (b \cdot 4^{n-1}k)^3 \cdot a + \frac{4 \cdot 3}{1 \cdot 2} (b \cdot 4^{n-1}k)^2 a^2 \pm \frac{4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} (b \cdot 4^{n-1})^1 a^3 + a^4 \\ &= a^4 + b \cdot 4^n (\dots) \\ &\equiv a^4 \pmod{b \cdot 4^n} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $x = b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a$ satisfies the congruence and hence is a solution of it.

For $k = 4$, $x = b \cdot 4^{n-1} \cdot 4 \pm a = b \cdot 4^n \pm a \equiv \pm a \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$ which is same as $k = 0$.

Similarly, for $k = 5, 6, 7$, it can be seen that the solutions are the same as for $k = 1, 2, 3$.

Therefore, all the solutions are obtained for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

Hence, the congruence has exactly eight solutions.

Sometimes the congruence is of the type: $x^4 \equiv b \pmod{m}$ with $b \neq a^4$.

If the congruence is solvable, then it can be written as: $x^4 \equiv b + k \cdot m \pmod{m}$

$$\equiv a^4 \pmod{m}, \text{ if } b + k \cdot m = a^4 \text{ for some } k \text{ [4].}$$

Then the solutions are given as the formula established.

ILLUSTRATIONS

Consider the congruence: $x^4 \equiv 113 \pmod{256}$.

It can be written as: $x^4 \equiv 113 + 2 \cdot 256 = 625 = 5^4 \pmod{4^4}$.

It is of the type $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n}$ with $a = 5, n = 4$.

Its solutions are given by $x \equiv 4^{n-1}k \pm a \pmod{4^n}$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\equiv 4^3k \pm 5 \pmod{4^4} \\ &\equiv 64k \pm 5 \pmod{256} \\ &\equiv \pm 5, 59, 69, 123, 133, 187, 197 \pmod{256}. \\ &\equiv 5, 251; 59, 69; 123, 133; 187, 197 \pmod{256} \end{aligned}$$

Consider the congruence $x^4 \equiv 1 \pmod{80}$.

Here, $80 = 5 \cdot 16 = 5 \cdot 4^2$

Then the congruence becomes $x^4 \equiv 1^4 \pmod{5 \cdot 4^2}$.

It is of the type: $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$ with $a = 1, b = 5, n = 2$.

The solutions are given by $x \equiv b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\equiv 5 \cdot 4^{2-1}k \pm 1 \pmod{5 \cdot 4^2} \\ &\equiv 20k \pm 1 \pmod{80} \\ &\equiv \pm 1; 19, 21; 39, 41; 59, 61 \pmod{80}. \\ &\equiv 1, 79; 19, 21; 39, 41; 59, 61 \pmod{80}. \end{aligned}$$

Consider the congruence $x^4 \equiv 16 \pmod{384}$.

Here $384 = 6 \cdot 64 = 6 \cdot 4^3$.

The congruence can be written as $x^4 \equiv 2^4 \pmod{6 \cdot 4^3}$.

It is of the type: $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$ with $a = 2, b = 6, n = 3$.

Then the solutions are given by $x \equiv b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\equiv 6 \cdot 4^2 \cdot k \pm 2 \pmod{6 \cdot 4^3} \\ &\equiv 96k \pm 2 \pmod{384} \\ &\equiv \pm 2; 94, 98, 190, 194; 286; 290 \pmod{384}. \\ &\equiv 2, 382; 94, 98; 190, 194; 286; 290 \pmod{384}. \end{aligned}$$

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the congruence under consideration

(1) $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{4^n}$

(2) $x^4 \equiv a^4 \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}; b \neq 4l$

Each has exactly eight incongruent solutions given by

(1) $x \equiv 4^{n-1} \cdot k \pm a \pmod{4^n}; k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

(2) $x \equiv b \cdot 4^{n-1}k \pm a \pmod{b \cdot 4^n}; k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

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MERIT OF THE PAPER

First time, some classes of standard solvable bi-quadratic congruence are formulated. Formulation made the finding of solutions easy. No need to use CRT. Formulation is the merit of the paper. It saves the time of calculations.

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